

1 **Behaviour of Rh supported on hydroxyapatite catalysts in partial oxidation**
2 **and steam reforming of methane: On the role of the speciation of the Rh**
3 **particles**

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1 **Abstract**

2 Rh/hydroxyapatite samples were prepared by impregnation and investigated for the
3 partial oxidation (POM) and steam reforming (SRM) of methane. The catalysts were
4 analysed by BET, XRD, DRS, XPS, H₂-TPR, TEM, H₂ chemisorption, CO₂-TPD and
5 NH₃-TPD techniques. The characterisation results showed that, after calcination, Rh
6 existed in three different forms in the samples: (i) large crystallites of Rh₂O₃ deposited
7 on the surface of the catalysts, (ii) RhO_x in small particles exhibiting strong interaction
8 with the support and (iii) a phase of Rh²⁺ species which incorporated the hydroxyapatite
9 framework.

10 Operating in the POM and SRM processes the reduced Rh(x)/HAP catalysts resulted
11 highly active and exhibited excellent stability at 973 K (for 30 h). This behaviour was
12 explained by their high coke-resistance. The activity of the catalyst with the optimum
13 loading (1%), in SRM, was compared with that of a commercial Rh/Al₂O₃ catalyst. The
14 conversion and H₂ and CO yields values achieved on the former were all close to those
15 exhibited by the latter. This comparable behaviour was explained by suitable properties
16 provided by the HAP support such as reducibility, lower surface acidity and larger pore
17 sizes (ensuring a better diffusion of the reactants and the products during the SRM
18 reaction). These properties seemed to compensate the low dispersion of the Rh active
19 phase induced by its low specific surface area.

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23 **Keywords:** Hydroxyapatite, Rh species, methane, partial oxidation, steam reforming.

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1 **1. Introduction**

2 Currently, the technologies applied for methane reforming for synthesis gas production
3 consist of steam reforming (SRM), partial oxidation (POM) and oxidative steam
4 reforming (OSRM) [1]. The choice of the appropriate technology is based on the
5 posterior use of the synthesis gas (H₂ and CO). For instance, hydrogen for fuel cell
6 applications is mainly produced by the endothermic SRM (1), providing high H₂/CO
7 ratio (≥ 3), before its subsequent purification. However, the exothermic POM (2) is the
8 suitable technology for Fischer-Tropsch synthesis which requires a syngas mixture with
9 H₂/CO ratio close to 2. Furthermore, for many applications OSRM is a strategy of
10 choice where SRM and POM processes could be efficiently coupled [1]. By adjusting
11 the O/C ratio of the inlet gas mixture the latter strategy can allow the control of the
12 process heat and the distribution of the products.

13 For methane reforming processes, Ni and a variety of noble metals (Ru, Rh, Pd, Ir, Pt)
14 are used as the active phases. For economic considerations, Ni is the most widely used;
15 however, it presents high susceptibility to sintering which causes coke deposition and,
16 then, a deactivation of its active sites [1-4]. Though many formulations were
17 investigated in order to enhance their dispersion, the stability of Ni catalysts is still
18 lower than that exhibited by the noble metals. This is because of their low specific
19 activity which requires the preparation of catalysts with high Ni loadings (> 15%) [1-4].
20 Among the noble metals, Rh has been found to be an excellent catalyst for the methane
21 reforming reactions. Data from the literature show that over the Rh catalysts the values
22 of the activation energy for POM (38-55 kJ mol⁻¹) are significantly lower than for SRM
23 (109 kJ mol⁻¹) [5].

1 Usually, the Rh active phases are supported on chemically active or inert metal oxides
2 presenting high specific surface area. Besides their high initial activity, the Rh catalysts
3 prove a very good stability due to their high resistance against carbon formation, even in
4 the demanding dry reforming process [6]. In order to improve, even more, the
5 performance of the Rh catalysts, current research is mainly focused on the examination
6 of the influence of the nature of the support on their activity and selectivity. In this
7 sense, Rh was deposited on various materials, such as Al₂O₃, TiO₂, CeO₂, MgO, La₂O₃,
8 SiO₂, ZrO₂ and ZSM-5 with the aim of finding suitable interactions metal-support
9 [5,7,8-13]. According to many reports, irrespective of the employed oxidant (O₂ or
10 H₂O), the methane reforming activity is sensitive to the type of these interactions which
11 strongly affect the Rh dispersion, its oxidation state and the acid-base properties of the
12 surface [5,10]. However, the nature of the active Rh species in POM is a subject of
13 controversy. For instance, in their study on the Rh/Al₂O₃ catalysts Buyevskaya et al.
14 [11] found that a high degree of surface reduction was necessary for high hydrogen
15 yield. By contrast, other reports showed that during POM at 973 K the Rh active species
16 consist of the metallic crystallites and partially reduced oxide clusters dispersed in the
17 rhodium metal matrix [12].

18 In their study on the activity of Rh/MgO-Al₂O₃ catalysts in SRM reaction Wang et al.
19 [13] reported that CH₄ turnover rate decreased with increasing Rh crystallite size
20 evidencing the structure sensitivity towards methane steam reforming over the range of
21 Rh crystalline size examined (5-15 nm). Ligthart et al. [10] studied the influence of Rh
22 particle sizes (using ZrO₂, CeO₂, CeZrO₂ and SiO₂ as supports) on the catalytic
23 performance in SRM. They pointed out that the nature of the support influenced the
24 dispersion and the reduction degree of the metal phase. They also observed that,
25 irrespective of the used support, catalysts with Rh nanoparticles smaller than 2.5 nm

1 deactivated more strongly than catalysts with larger nanoparticles. The observed
2 deactivation was explained by the oxidation of very small particles of Rh under the
3 SRM conditions.

4 In the present work, we investigate the textural, structural and chemical properties of a
5 series of Rh/hydroxyapatite catalysts for their application in two methane reforming
6 processes (POM and SRM). We chose hydroxyapatite (HAP: $\text{Ca}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$) for
7 study because of its interesting characteristics and catalytic properties. It is known that
8 HAP can form synergistic interactions with a variety of transition metals because of its
9 high ion-exchange capacity [14-19]. Moreover, the apatite structure tolerates large
10 deviation from stoichiometry. For instance, Ca-deficient hydroxyapatite exhibits
11 peculiar structural rearrangement for charge compensation with formation of cation
12 (Ca^{2+}) and anion (OH) vacancies. Despite of the fact that a number of studies dealing
13 with HAP support are presently available, to the best of our knowledge, the catalytic
14 properties of Rh/HAP samples in the POM and SRM reactions have not been yet
15 investigated.

16

17 **2. Experimental**

18 Non-stoichiometric hydroxyapatite support (HAP) was synthesised using a protocol
19 reported elsewhere [14-19]. The Rh/HAP catalysts were prepared by impregnation
20 using solutions containing three different amounts of $\text{RhCl}_3 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ precursor. The
21 impregnated samples were dried in air at 120 °C for 12 h and subsequently calcined for
22 4 h, at 1000 K. The obtained samples will be hereafter referred as Rh(x)/HAP (x = 0.5,
23 1 and 2wt.%).

24 The characterisation of the prepared samples involved a wide number of techniques
25 including BET, TEM, XRD, H_2 -TPR, DRS, XPS and volumetric adsorption of NH_3 and

1 CO₂ (at 313 K) as well-known probe molecules for acid and basic sites, respectively.
2 The experimental details of each analytical technique are described elsewhere [14-16].
3 The morphology, size and dispersion of the rhodium particles on the reduced
4 Rh(x)/HAP were analysed by transmission electron microscopy. The corresponding
5 experiments were performed on a Philips CM200 transmission electron microscope
6 equipped with LaB6 filament operating at 200 kV and combined with X-ray energy
7 dispersive spectroscopy (X-EDS) techniques. The average diameter calculations of the
8 rhodium particles were made from the measurement of at least 150 particles using
9 ImageJ software. The values of Rh dispersion and metallic surface area were calculated
10 according to a procedure described by Borodzinski and Bonarowska. [20].

11 The dispersion of the Rh particles was also determined by H₂ chemisorption techniques.
12 The experiments were carried out on Micromeritics AutoChem 2920 instrument
13 equipped with a thermal conductivity detector (TCD). The catalysts (100 mg) were
14 submitted to a reduction at 1000 K (1 h) in a flow 5% H₂/Ar (50 cm³ min⁻¹) before
15 cooling to 313 K under Ar. H₂ pulses (5% H₂/Ar, loop volume: 0.5 cm³) were then
16 injected in Ar carrier (50 cm³ min⁻¹) over the sample, at 313 K. The Rh dispersion, D,
17 defined as the active metal fraction exposed was determined on the assumption of a
18 unity adsorption stoichiometry (H/Rh = 1). The average size of the Rh particles was
19 calculated, assuming that the Rh particles have a spherical shape, as follows [20]:

20 i) For low Rh dispersion (< 20%): $d(\text{nm}) = 1.34/D$ (3)

21 ii) For high Rh dispersion ($\geq 20\%$): $d(\text{nm}) = 0.89/D^{1.23}$ (4)

22 The POM and SRM catalytic tests over the Rh(x)/HAP catalysts were performed, with
23 the same gas hourly space velocity (GHSV), 19,200 cm³ CH₄ g⁻¹ h⁻¹, in a tubular flow
24 reactor, with a diameter of 9 mm (linear gas velocity higher than 20 cm s⁻¹), operating at
25 atmospheric pressure, using 250 mg of the catalyst and a total feed gas mixture of 800

1 $\text{cm}^3 \text{min}^{-1}$. The reactor was located inside a furnace in which the temperature was
 2 controlled with a thermocouple placed in the catalyst bed. In order to distribute the
 3 excess heat through the catalytic bed, thereby reducing the presence of small local hot
 4 spots, the catalyst particles (250-300 μm) were diluted with inert quartz (750 mg)
 5 reaching a total bed length of 16 mm. For comparison, the activity of a commercial
 6 Rh/Al₂O₃ catalyst with 1% Rh (Alfa Aesar) was also studied. For the POM reaction
 7 experiments the reactive gas mixture was composed of 10% CH₄ and 5% O₂ (O/C = 1)
 8 balanced with N₂. The SRM catalytic tests (H₂O/C = 3) were performed with a feed gas
 9 mixture composed of 10%CH₄ and 30%H₂O balanced with N₂. Prior to running the
 10 experiments, the catalysts were submitted to a high-temperature reduction step at 1000
 11 K (1 h) in a flow 5%H₂/N₂. The temperature of the reaction was increased from 773 K
 12 to 1000 K with a heating rate of 3 K min⁻¹. In order to investigate the stability of the
 13 catalysts, additional experiments were carried out at a constant temperature (973 K) for
 14 about 30 h. The reaction products were continuously analysed by a gas chromatograph
 15 equipped with a TCD detector. Methane conversion and H₂, CO and CO₂ yields
 16 (X(CH₄), Y(H₂), Y(CO) and Y(CO₂), respectively) were calculated by using the
 17 corresponding inlet and outlet molar flow values (Eqs. (5), (6), (7) and (8),
 18 respectively):

$$19 \quad X(\text{CH}_4), \% = \frac{F(\text{CO}_{,out}) + F(\text{CO}_{2,out})}{F(\text{CH}_{4,in})} \cdot 100 \quad (5)$$

$$20 \quad Y(\text{H}_2) = \frac{F(\text{H}_{2,out})}{2 \cdot F(\text{CH}_{4,in})} \quad (6)$$

$$21 \quad Y(\text{CO}) = \frac{F(\text{CO}_{,out})}{F(\text{CH}_{4,in})} \quad (7)$$

$$22 \quad Y(\text{CO}_2) = \frac{F(\text{CO}_{2,out})}{F(\text{CH}_{4,in})} \quad (8)$$

1 The elemental balance was checked by calculation of the difference between the total
2 amounts of the inlet and outlet carbon-containing molecules. The thermodynamic data
3 were calculated via the HSC Chemistry software package by the GIBBS programme
4 using the so-called Gibbs Energy Minimization Method. The substances to be taken into
5 account in the calculations, the amount of reactants, the potentially stable phases as well
6 as the temperature of raw species were specified as input. In addition to solid carbon,
7 the following substances in the gas phase were considered: CH₄, O₂, N₂, CO, CO₂,
8 H₂ and H₂O.

9

10 **3. Results and discussion**

11 **3.1. N₂-physorption (BET measurements)**

12 The N₂ physisorption isotherms recorded at 77 K for the support and the three Rh
13 samples are included as supplementary material (Fig. S1). The observed isotherms and
14 the hysteresis loops typology of all catalysts were similar. Data obtained from the
15 analysis of the isotherms corresponding to the calcined and reduced samples are
16 summarised in Table 1 and Fig. 1. The pore size distribution of the HAP bare support
17 consisted of a broad peak centred at 53 nm. Interestingly, after reduction, the latter
18 became narrower and shifted towards lower value (38 nm). This behaviour could be
19 associated with structural changes induced by the reduction process. Regarding the
20 effect of the Rh content on the specific surface area, a slight decrease in the S_{BET} was
21 observed on the reduced Rh(0.5)/HAP (26 m² g⁻¹) and Rh(2)/HAP (25 m² g⁻¹) catalysts
22 when compared with that measured on the HAP bare support (33 m² g⁻¹). By contrast,
23 the deposition of 1% Rh did not induce a significant change in the S_{BET}, which was
24 around 30 m² g⁻¹. The difference between the three Rh catalysts might be related with a
25 distinct evolution of the surface phases and/or the dispersion of the Rh species. In

1 parallel, as reported in Fig. 1, the progressive addition of Rh induced a significant
2 increase in the broadness of the peak around 50 nm. The curves corresponding to the
3 Rh(1)/HAP and Rh(2)/HAP catalysts also showed a shoulder between 30-40 nm
4 indicating an heterogeneity of their surface. As will be shown later, the observed
5 changes with the Rh loading increase could be associated with an increase of the Rh
6 species particle sizes. Nevertheless, when reduced at 1000 K, all Rh samples did not
7 show significant changes in their pore size distribution.

8

9 **3.2. X-ray diffraction (XRD)**

10 The XRD diagrams of the Rh(x)/HAP samples compared with that of HAP bare support
11 are shown in Fig. 2. The indexation of the diffraction peaks of the synthesised HAP
12 sample confirmed the formation of a unique phase, identical to hydroxyapatite structure
13 (JCPDS 01-082-2956). The estimation of the average size of the HAP particles, by
14 means of Scherrer equation, showed that it was around 49 nm. Moreover, its degree of
15 crystallinity was estimated to be around 0.98. The latter value was significantly higher
16 than that reported in our previous study on HAP samples calcined at 773 K which was
17 around 0.80 [16]. This improvement in the cristallinity of the HAP with the increase of
18 the calcination temperature was in good agreement with the results found by Kim et al.
19 [21]. After reduction of HAP support at 1000 K the structure remained unchanged;
20 however a significant decrease in the crystallite size, from 49 to 32 nm, could be noted
21 (Table 1). This evolution could explain the observed shift in the pore size distribution
22 towards lower values (Fig. 1). This effect was also accompanied by a slight decrease in
23 the HAP lattice parameters. This corresponded to a lattice reduction of the apatite
24 structure of about 0.1%. Since the reduction of Ca^{2+} was discarded, the observed change
25 was associated with a possible increase in the density of the oxygen vacancy [22-23].

1 According to Bystrov et al. [23] there are various possible oxygen vacancies in the
2 apatite lattice: O from PO₄, O from OH, the loss of an entire OH group, or the
3 simultaneous loss of O from PO₄ and an entire OH group.

4 As expected, due to its low concentrations ($\leq 2\%$), the diffractograms of Rh-doped HAP
5 catalysts, in their oxidised and reduced forms, showed no lines attributed to Rh phases
6 (Fig. 2). However, a clear evolution in the positions of the HAP diffraction peaks, with
7 Rh addition could be noticed (Fig. 2); thereby suggesting a modification in the cell
8 parameters of the HAP crystal. Table 1 lists the corresponding values calculated for all
9 Rh(x)/HAP samples. The reported data revealed a significant increase in the “a”
10 parameter and the volume of the lattice with increasing the Rh content which could be
11 attributed to a possible incorporation of Rh species into the HAP framework. Since the
12 ionic radius of Rh (0.20 nm) is smaller than that of Ca (0.23 nm), the observed
13 expansion was explained by an incorporation of Rh into the cationic vacant sites rather
14 than an ion-exchange process with Ca²⁺ sites. A similar observation could be found in
15 our previous study dealing with Pd/HAP samples [16]. After reduction the Rh(x)/HAP
16 patterns showed the presence of an additional peak at 30.7° with a low intensity.
17 Interestingly, this feature was more pronounced in the case of the Rh(0.5)/HAP and the
18 Rh(2)/HAP samples. A comparison of the observed peak with reference data evidenced
19 a transformation of a small fraction of the hydroxyapatite structure into tricalcium
20 phosphate (TCP: Ca₃(PO₄)₂) phase (JCPDS 00-009-0348). This effect could be
21 explained by a possible acceleration of HAP→TCP transition due to the reduction of the
22 Rh species incorporating the HAP framework. A more careful analysis of the patterns of
23 the Rh(2)/HAP sample revealed that the intensity ratio ($I_{\text{TCP}}/I_{\text{HAP}}$) of the most intense
24 peaks corresponding to TCP₍₁₇₀₎ and HAP₍₂₁₁₎, respectively, differed from that of
25 Rh(0.5)/HAP and Rh(1)/HAP catalysts. Indeed, the value of this ratio was about 5.2%

1 for the Rh(1)/HAP, 6.2% for the Rh(0.5)/HAP; whereas it increased up to 9% for the
2 Rh(2)/HAP catalyst. The high contribution of the TCP phase in the latter could be
3 associated with the incorporation of large amounts of Rh in the HAP framework.
4 Moreover, we thought that this structure transformation might be responsible for the
5 loss in the S_{BET} noticed, especially, for the Rh(0.5)/HAP and Rh(2)/HAP catalysts.

6

7 **3.3. Temperature programmed reduction (H_2 -TPR)**

8 H_2 -TPR experiments were carried out in order to investigate the reducibility of the
9 calcined HAP support and the different Rh species (Fig. 3). The diagram of the bare
10 support was characterised by the presence of an intense peak centred at 705 K with a H_2
11 uptake around $209.1 \mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$. According to many reports, the latter was probably due
12 to the consumption of surface oxygen anions species [24-27]. Moreover, these species
13 could be restored by a simple reoxidation of the sample [27]. In order to evaluate this
14 possibility the HAP sample was subjected to a second H_2 -TPR experiment after its
15 reoxidation at 1000 K (Fig. S2). The results evidenced a striking similarity between the
16 two successive H_2 -TPR profiles in terms of the peak position and the H_2 uptake, thus
17 confirming the reversibility of the redox process.

18 Besides the HAP reduction peak, the H_2 -TPR profiles corresponding to the calcined Rh
19 catalysts were characterised by the presence of additional uptakes due to the reduction
20 of at least three different species of Rh. It is worth noting that the HAP reduction peak
21 shifted towards lower temperatures (680-690 K) in the presence of the Rh species.
22 Similar behaviour was observed in previous studies dealing with Rh/ CeO_2 systems
23 [8,9]. For instance, Varga et al. [8] reported that the oxidised CeO_2 surface could release
24 oxygen easily in the presence of Rh accompanied by the reduction of the noble metal.
25 At low temperatures, < 600 K, the spectra showed two peaks, named α and β , in the

1 temperature ranges of 445-460 K and 490-550 K, respectively. Generally, the presence
2 of the former is associated with the reduction of dispersed Rh_2O_3 species whereas the
3 latter could be attributed to the reduction of Rh species exhibiting a relatively low
4 interaction with the support [28-30]. It is worth nothing that the intensity of the
5 β species peak seems to increase with Rh loading which might be associated with the
6 growth of Rh particles. On the other hand, the peak at significantly higher temperatures
7 (γ), > 873 K, was due to the reduction of the Rh species presenting much stronger
8 interactions with the support. The occurrence of such feature was found in previous
9 studies on different systems [28-30]. For instance, Ruckenstein et al. [28] observed in
10 the reduction spectra of Rh/ La_2O_3 , Rh/MgO, Rh/ Y_2O_3 and Rh/ Ta_2O_5 a high temperature
11 peak associated with the reduction of LaRhO_3 , MgRh_2O_4 , YRhO_3 and RhTaO_4 species,
12 respectively. Moreover, Rice et al. [31] evidenced the stability of Rh^{2+} ions species in
13 the framework of ZSM-5 occupying sites located in the walls of the channels. The
14 presence of stable Rh^{2+} species was also suggested in the case of Rh/ Al_2O_3 systems
15 when rhodium diffuses into the support forming a rhodium spinel [32]. Therefore, in
16 good agreement with these previous studies, the high temperature peak observed in our
17 H_2 -TPR profiles could be assigned to Rh^{2+} species which incorporated the
18 hydroxyapatite network. This conclusion was supported by analysing the values of
19 H_2/Rh molar ratios determined by the integration of all Rh reduction peaks (Table 2).
20 Indeed, the corresponding values (1.2-1.3) showed that they were lower than those
21 expected for a complete reduction of Rh^{3+} in Rh_2O_3 species (1.5) thereby the presence
22 of a fraction of Rh with a lower oxidation state (probably Rh^{2+}). It should be noted that
23 this possible incorporation of Rh was also assessed by XRD techniques.

24 Table 2 also reports the quantification of H_2 uptake corresponding to α , β and γ species.
25 The results revealed that the distribution of Rh species among the different sites did not

1 depend on the Rh content. For instance, the incorporated amounts of Rh exhibited the
2 lowest contribution (17%) on the Rh(1)/HAP sample, whereas they presented higher
3 values on the Rh(0.5)/HAP (26%) and Rh(2)/HAP (22%). This suggested that these two
4 samples were more prone to incorporate the Rh into the HAP structure. It is also worth
5 nothing that this difference could explain the resistance of the Rh(1)/HAP sample
6 against the loss in surface area.

7

8 **3.4. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS)**

9 The chemical composition and the distribution of the Rh species laying on the surface
10 of the calcined Rh(x)/HAP catalysts were investigated by means of XPS
11 techniques. Fig. 4 and Table 3 summarise the corresponding results. The value of the
12 surface Ca/P atomic ratio of the bare support (1.5) was in good agreement with the bulk
13 analysis (Table 3). Among all Rh catalysts, the Rh(0.5)/HAP sample presented an
14 exception since it exhibited a slightly higher Ca/P ratio (1.6). This suggested that the Ca
15 species were more exposed to the surface than the other two samples. Previous studies
16 have evidenced a direct relationship between the variation in the Ca/P ratio and the
17 drastic changes in the chemical properties of the hydroxyapatite [33]. The effect of the
18 observed Ca/P increase on the acid-base properties of the prepared materials will be
19 commented below.

20 The XPS spectra of all Rh(x)/HAP catalysts, in the Rh 3d_{5/2} and Rh 3d_{3/2} regions,
21 displayed two main peaks centred at 307.8 ± 0.1 eV and 312.4 ± 0.2 eV, respectively
22 (Fig. 4 and Table 3). The Rh 3d_{5/2} binding energy values seemed to be lower than 308.1-
23 308.6 eV expected for Rh³⁺ species [32,34]. In accordance with Ref. [8], the observed
24 shift could be due to the final state effect and/or strong metal-support interactions.
25 Besides the occurrence of Rh³⁺ species, these values revealed the presence of Rh²⁺

1 species; since the corresponding binding energy were peaked between that of Rh⁰ (307
2 eV) and Rh³⁺ (308.1-308.6) states [32,34]. Nevertheless, the position of these features
3 seemed to depend, systematically, on the Rh content. For instance, in the spectrum of
4 the sample with the lowest Rh loading (0.5%) the observed 3d_{5/2} peak was centred at
5 307.9 eV; whereas it shifted towards lower binding energies in the case of the Rh-rich
6 samples (307.8 eV for Rh(1)/HAP and 307.7 eV for Rh(2)/HAP). As reported in
7 previous studies [15], this negative shift of the core level spectra was consistent with a
8 decrease in the metal-support interaction with an increased Rh loading. Moreover, the
9 calculated difference between the energy positions corresponding to 3d_{3/2} and 3d_{5/2}
10 peaks also evidenced a systematic variation in the spin-orbit splitting (4.7 eV for
11 Rh(0.5)/HAP, 4.6 eV for Rh(1)/HAP and 4.5 eV for Rh(2)/HAP). Table 3 also
12 compares the concentrations of Rh determined in the bulk (ICP) and the near surface
13 (XPS) of the catalysts. Exclusively, the Rh(2)/HAP sample exhibited a lower surface Rh
14 amount (1.4%) compared with that determined by ICP (2%), thus suggesting a low
15 dispersion of the Rh particles.

16

17 **3.5. Diffuse reflectance spectroscopy (DRS)**

18 Diffuse reflectance spectroscopy was used to study the symmetry and the coordination
19 of rhodium species dispersed on the HAP support. Fig. 5 displays the optical absorption
20 spectra, for the oxidised Rh(x)/HAP catalysts, recorded in the range 200-1200 nm. For
21 the sake of comparison, the spectrum of the Rh(2)/HAP sample reduced at 773 K was
22 also included. The attribution of the absorption bands was carried out by comparison
23 with spectra of earlier studies dealing with rhodium complexes [35-43].

24 It is known that the trivalency is definitely the most stable oxidation number among Rh
25 ions in oxides [35]. The typical spectrum of Rh³⁺ (4d⁶) is composed of two bands in the

1 visible domain describing two allowed d-d transitions (${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1T_{1g}$ (at 535 nm) and ${}^1A_{1g}$
2 $\rightarrow {}^1T_{2g}$ (at 420 nm)) [35,36,43]. The Rh^{2+} ($3d^7$) ions also exhibit a simple spectrum that
3 involves two d-d transitions (${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{1g}$ and ${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$) appearing in the visible
4 domain. Groller-Walrand et al. [43] evidenced, experimentally, the absorption of these
5 features, having approximately the same energy, between 500-600 nm. Rh^{4+} ($4d^5$) and
6 Rh^{5+} ($4d^4$), however, when doped into oxide matrices give, besides the visible region
7 bands between 400-800 nm, an absorption band in the NIR wavelength region
8 [37,41,42]. In their study on the evolution of the oxidation states of Rh, Kaczmarek et
9 al. [37] attributed the absorption around 650 nm to Rh^{4+} species and around 800 nm to
10 Rh^{5+} species. Furthermore, according to many reports, the existence of two Rh
11 oxidation states induces an interaction between their respective sites and leads to
12 additional absorption bands due to metal to metal charge transfer in the visible and/or
13 NIR domain [35,38,42].

14 The spectrum of HAP bare support exhibited a weak band centred at 310 nm which was
15 assigned to Ca-O charge transfer [15, 16]. Interestingly, the visible region was
16 characterised by the presence of two bands at 520 nm and 740 nm. The occurrence of
17 the latter was in good agreement with the optical bands attributed to the presence of OH
18 vacancy in the hydroxyapatite structure [23]. This result was expected since the
19 prepared support presented a deficiency in Ca^{2+} which was probably compensated by
20 the addition of H^+ and/or removal of OH^- ions [15].

21 The spectra of Rh(x)/HAP catalysts were characterised by the presence of a weak band
22 at 220 nm attributed to Rh-O charge transfer [36,40] and a broad asymmetric band in
23 the visible region. The latter seemed to be broader on the Rh(0.5)/HAP and Rh(2)/HAP
24 spectra compared with that of the Rh(1)/HAP. Interestingly, in good agreement with the
25 H_2 -TPR and XPS results, the absence of high wavelength bands (above 650 nm)

1 demonstrated that Rh^{3+} and/or Rh^{2+} were the dominant valence states. It should be noted
2 that, as the concentration of Rh increased, the samples colour changed from light pink-
3 brown for Rh(0.5)/HAP to dark gray-brown for Rh(1)/HAP and dark gray (which is
4 typical of the Rh_2O_3 species) in the case of Rh(2)/HAP. The observed changes indicated
5 an apparent abundance of bulk Rh_2O_3 with Rh loading. In order to confirm the presence
6 of the Rh^{2+} species incorporated in the HAP structure the Rh(2)/HAP sample was
7 reduced at 773 K and then analysed by DRS. We assumed that this temperature was
8 sufficiently high for reduction of all Rh^{3+} species while the incorporated Rh species
9 could keep their cationic form (Rh^{2+}). Indeed, as shown in Fig. 5, the corresponding
10 spectrum only showed an absorption band in the visible region, centred at 575 nm,
11 evidencing the presence of Rh^{2+} species [43]. This was actually a relevant observation,
12 not reported as yet, which confirmed that DRS is, indeed, a powerful tool providing
13 valuable information about the nature of the ionic species of Rh.

14

15 **3.6. Morphology and dispersion of the Rh particles**

16 Hydroxyapatite-supported rhodium samples, reduced at 1000 K, were investigated by
17 TEM techniques. Fig. 6 displays the corresponding TEM images and the particle size
18 distribution traces. Examination of the Rh(0.5)/HAP sample revealed the presence of
19 spherical Rh particles dispersed on the support surface. Furthermore, the corresponding
20 size distribution diagram consisted of a broad distribution with an average size of
21 12.8 nm and a dispersion of 10.6% (Table 4). Interestingly, the Rh(1)/HAP sample
22 exhibited the highest dispersion (11.6%) with an average size close to 11.6 nm. At high
23 Rh loading the particle sizes presented a marked heterogeneity. Moreover, the addition
24 of 2 wt.% Rh resulted in the deposition of larger particle sizes (16.2 nm) corresponding
25 to a dispersion of 8.3%.

1 Table 4 also lists the Rh dispersion (D_{chem}), active Rh surface area and average particle
2 size (d_{chem}) for the Rh(x)/HAP catalysts as determined by H_2 chemisorption
3 measurements at 313 K. In this case, the dispersion measured on series of the catalysts
4 seemed to follow this general trend: Rh(0.5)/HAP (17%) > Rh(1)/HAP (9.6%) >
5 Rh(2)/HAP (6.4%). The comparison of these values with those determined by TEM
6 techniques showed slight differences in the case of the Rh(1)/HAP and Rh(2)/HAP
7 catalysts. By contrast, on the Rh(0.5)/HAP catalyst the measured Rh dispersion resulted
8 significantly higher (17%) compared to that determined by TEM techniques (10.6%).
9 This could be explained by a possible presence of a fraction of very small particles
10 accessible to the gas phase; but not detectable by TEM techniques.

11 On the basis of the Rh surface density, calculated as the number of Rh atoms per
12 support unit surface area, the Rh dispersion values were compared with those
13 corresponding to different supports, reported in the literature [6,7,13,44-46]. According
14 to Fig. S3, the values of the Rh dispersion determined on the Rh(x)/HAP catalysts were
15 in good concordance with the general tendency found for a series of Rh catalysts
16 exhibiting different surface areas.

17

18 **3.7. Acid-base properties of the Rh(x)/HAP catalysts**

19 The basic properties of the reduced Rh(x)/HAP catalysts were characterised by means
20 of CO_2 -TPD techniques. Fig. 7a shows the desorption profiles recorded on the samples
21 after pre-adsorption of CO_2 at 313 K for 1 h and flushed with He at 313 K (2 h). The
22 CO_2 -TPD trace for the bare support consisted of three desorption peaks centred at 400,
23 560 and 850 K, which evidenced the presence of three adsorption sites exhibiting
24 different thermal stability. Rhodium deposition induced significant changes affecting
25 both the amount and the thermal stability of the adsorbed CO_2 . At low temperatures, the

1 progressive addition of Rh increased the broadness of the first peak (400 K) and
2 provoked its splitting into two peaks centred at 390 K and 435 K. The latter could be
3 associated with the appearance of new weak adsorption sites. Moreover, the presence of
4 Rh seemed to shift the second desorption peak towards lower temperatures, from 560 K
5 to 520 K, suggesting an apparent weakening of these medium-strength basic sites. At
6 high temperatures, the desorption of CO₂ from the strong basic sites was still peaked at
7 850 K; however, the corresponding amounts of chemisorbed CO₂ seemed to decrease
8 with the Rh loading.

9 Table 5 lists quantitative data corresponding to total surface density of the adsorption
10 sites and the distribution of the basic sites classified according to their strength (weak,
11 medium-strength and strong basic sites). These values were determined by integration
12 of the bands centred at three temperature ranges (390-440 K, 500-600 K and >700 K,
13 respectively). Some relevant conclusions might be drawn from the analysis of these
14 results. Hence, it was found that the deposition of 0.5 wt.% Rh onto the HAP increased
15 the total surface basic sites density from 2.7 to 3.1 $\mu\text{mol}_{\text{CO}_2} \text{m}^{-2}$. Since the basicity of
16 hydroxyapatite generally increases with an increase in the Ca/P ratio [16], we might
17 reasonably explain the high density of the Rh(0.5)/HAP basic sites by its surface
18 enrichment with the Ca species, as evidenced by XPS. However, at high Rh loadings, 1
19 wt.% and 2 wt.%, the density substantially decreased since it did not exceed 2.2 and
20 $2 \mu\text{mol}_{\text{CO}_2} \text{m}^{-2}$, respectively. It is worth noting that the contribution of the strong basic
21 sites decreased on all Rh samples which represented only 8-9% compared with 19%
22 determined on the HAP bare support. Silvester et al. [33] related the occurrence of
23 strong basic sites to the abundance of OH species on the hydroxyapatite surface. In this
24 sense, we thought that the deposition of Rh induced a dehydroxylation of the support
25 surface which might explain the observed decrease in the amounts of the strong basic

1 sites. Moreover, the effect of increasing the Rh content from 0.5 wt.% to 2 wt.% would
2 mainly be an increase in the weak basic sites fraction at the expense of the medium-
3 strength and strong adsorption sites. Indeed, the weak basic sites represented 26% on
4 the HAP bare support while they accounted for 28% on the Rh/(0.5)/HAP, 44% on the
5 Rh/(1)/HAP and 53% on the Rh/(2)/HAP catalyst.

6 Finally, the acid properties of the reduced samples were examined by means of NH₃-
7 TPD. Fig. 7b and Table 5 summarise the obtained results. The density of acid sites
8 measured on the bare support ($2.3 \mu\text{mol}_{\text{NH}_3} \text{m}^{-2}$) was markedly larger than that
9 determined for the rhodium-impregnated samples ($1.2\text{-}1.5 \mu\text{mol}_{\text{NH}_3} \text{m}^{-2}$). The NH₃-TPD
10 profiles corresponding to all analysed samples consisted of a main desorption peak,
11 assigned to weak acid sites, around 450-470 K.

12

13 **3.8. Catalytic activity**

14 **3.8.1. Partial oxidation of methane (POM)**

15 The POM reaction was carried out over the Rh(x)/HAP catalysts after in-situ reduction
16 at 1000 K. In order to ensure the reliability of the evolution of the temperature the
17 corresponding profiles were monitored for all catalytic runs. As shown in Fig. S4, when
18 the N₂ feed was switched to the POM gas mixture the temperature of the catalyst bed
19 increased from 773 to 812 K (within 3 min) before a gradual return to 773 K. We
20 assume that the observed increase in the temperature (by around 40 K) could be due to
21 the net exothermicity of the various reactions involved in the process (including total
22 oxidation of methane and subsequent reforming of methane with carbon dioxide and/or
23 water). This relatively low temperature increase was expected since the catalyst
24 particles were diluted with inert quartz (at a mass ratio of 1:3) in order to minimise the

1 occurrence of hot spots in the bed. Moreover, for all investigated reaction temperatures,
2 isothermal conditions were rapidly achieved.

3 Fig. 8(a-d) shows the corresponding results in terms of CH₄ conversion and H₂, CO and
4 CO₂ yields, respectively, in the temperature range 773-1000 K. It was noticed that, over
5 the whole temperature range, the Rh(1)/HAP sample exhibited the highest catalytic
6 performance. Table 6 compares the catalytic activity of the Rh samples, on the basis of
7 T₅₀ values. The reported data pointed out that the activity followed this general trend:
8 Rh(1)/HAP (860 K) > Rh(0.5)/HAP (886 K) > Rh(2)/HAP (910 K).

9 At 773 K the conversion with the most active catalyst was around 37% and it increased
10 to reach about 52% at 873 K and 72% at 1000 K (Fig. 8a). Likewise, the increase in the
11 reaction temperature promoted the H₂ yield, which attained the highest value (0.62) at
12 1000 K (Fig. 8b). In parallel, an increase in CO yield could be observed from 0.11 at
13 773 K to 0.62 at 1000 K (Fig. 8c). By contrast, the values of CO₂ yields decreased with
14 the temperature increase (Fig. 8d). For instance, over the Rh(1)/HAP catalyst the Y_{CO₂}
15 decreased from 0.25 at 773 K to 0.1 at 1000 K which suggested a lower contribution of
16 the methane combustion activity. In their study on the activity of Rh/alumina catalysts
17 Wang et al. [47] claimed that CO₂ could be formed from adsorbed CO by fast oxidation
18 with adsorbed oxygen or by the nucleophilic attack of adsorbed hydroxyl. It should be
19 noted that, despite exhibiting the highest metallic surface area (0.55 m² g⁻¹), compared
20 with those measured on Rh(0.5)/HAP (0.18 m² g⁻¹) and Rh(1)/HAP (0.38 m² g⁻¹), the
21 Rh(2)/HAP showed the poorest performance. Our TEM results revealed that, on the
22 three Rh catalysts, the mean particle sizes followed this trend: Rh(1)/HAP (11.6 nm) <
23 Rh(0.5)/HAP (12.8 nm) < Rh(2)/HAP (16.2 nm). This comparison pointed out the
24 structure sensitivity of the Rh particles spread over the HAP carrier. A comparison of
25 our results with those reported in a previous study [48] showed that lower methane

1 conversion values were obtained over Rh/SiO₂ systems which did not exceed 46% at
2 873 K (versus 53% over the Rh(1)/HAP catalyst). This comparison proved the potential
3 of HAP support as a good alternative.

4 Table 6 also lists the obtained H₂/CO and CO/CO₂ ratios calculated at 773 K, 873 K and
5 973 K over all tested catalysts. The analysis of the H₂/CO values evidenced, irrespective
6 of the used catalyst, an inverse dependence with temperature. Despite this behaviour the
7 H₂/CO values were in all cases higher than 2. This value was sufficiently high to hinder
8 the encapsulation of the metal particles by deposited carbon [1,49]. It is worth noting
9 that the resulted H₂/CO value (2.1) at 973 K is of great importance since it could be
10 suitable for a posterior use. For instance, Fischer-Tropsch synthesis requires an H₂/CO
11 ratio about 2.1 [50]. If not so, the excess hydrogen would have to be separated. On the
12 other hand, according to Table 6, the increase of the CO/CO₂ ratio values with the
13 reaction temperature could be explained by a main occurrence of the reverse water gas
14 shift reaction.

15 The catalytic stability of the most active catalysts (Rh(0.5)/HAP and Rh(1)/HAP) was
16 investigated by analysing the evolution of methane conversion and the products yields
17 with time on stream at 973 K for 30 h (Fig. 9). The two catalysts exhibited a very good
18 stability in the studied time on stream. The methane conversion values were around
19 68% over Rh(0.5)/HAP and 76% over the Rh(1)/HAP catalyst. The latter also kept its
20 superiority in terms of Y_{H₂} (0.69 vs. 0.56 over Rh(0.5)/HAP) and Y_{CO} (0.66 vs. 0.53
21 over Rh(0.5)/HAP). TPO-MS analyses performed in order to determine the amount of
22 carbon accumulated on the used catalysts showed that the deposited carbon masses were
23 lower than 1 wt.%. This was in good agreement with XRD analysis (not shown) of the
24 spent catalysts which confirmed the absence of the signals due to the formation of
25 carbon (graphite). Moreover, the two tested catalysts did not suffer significant changes

1 in their specific surface areas which remained almost constant. From these post-reaction
2 analyses we could explain the stability of the two catalysts by their excellent resistance
3 against coking.

4

5 **3.8.2. Steam reforming of methane (SRM)**

6 The reduced Rh(x)/HAP catalysts were also tested in the SRM reaction in the
7 temperature range of 773-1000 K. Due to the endothermic character of the process, just
8 after the gas feed mixture was admitted to the reactor the temperature catalyst bed
9 decreased, by about 15 K, from 773 to 760 K before a gradual return to 773 K (Fig. S5).
10 Fig. 10 (a-d) shows the profiles of CH₄ conversion and H₂, CO and CO₂ yields,
11 respectively, as a function of the reaction temperature. For reference purposes, a
12 commercial Rh/Al₂O₃ catalyst was also tested under similar experimental conditions.
13 Among the three investigated catalysts, supported on HAP, the highest values of
14 methane conversion and the H₂ and CO yields were given over the Rh(1)/HAP. Hence,
15 at 923 K, around 77% CH₄ conversion was achieved. In addition, it also gave the
16 highest values of Y_{H₂} (1.37) and Y_{CO} (0.41). These values demonstrated the superiority
17 of the Rh(1)/HAP when compared with those given by a 1%Rh/CeZr catalyst, reported
18 by Rabe et al. [50]. By contrast, the Rh(0.5)/HAP sample showed the poorest
19 performance; even at 973 K, the values corresponding to X_{CH₄}, Y_{H₂}, Y_{CO} and Y_{CO₂} did
20 not exceed 66%, 1.14, 0.33 and 0.33, respectively. It is worth outlining that both
21 conversion and yields achieved with the Rh(1)/HAP catalyst were close to the values
22 obtained over the commercial Rh/Al₂O₃ catalyst. The values of T₅₀ were relatively
23 similar on the two tested catalysts (845 K on the former and 830 K on the latter).
24 A comparison of the performance of the Rh(1)/HAP catalyst in POM and SRM
25 reactions showed that, at low temperatures (< 873 K), replacing oxygen with steam

1 resulted in both lower methane conversion and CO yield while it improved the
2 H₂ production. At high temperatures (≥ 873 K), by contrast, an increase in the overall
3 activity as well as H₂ yield were observed. In parallel, the calculated H₂/CO ratio was,
4 in all investigated temperatures, higher than 5.6 (Table 6). Furthermore, in the presence
5 of steam, the assayed catalysts gave considerable amounts of CO₂ suggesting the main
6 occurrence of water gas shift reaction. For instance, at 973 K, the SRM gas mixture
7 gave Y_{CO₂} values ranged between 0.3-0.4 whereas they were lower than 0.15 in the
8 POM process.

9 In order to investigate the stability of the Rh catalysts in the SRM reaction, additional
10 experiments were carried out, at 973 K, for a considerably more prolonged reaction time
11 interval (30 h) (Fig. 11). As a general behaviour, all samples were markedly stable. The
12 results also evidenced that the Rh(1)/HAP maintained its superiority in terms of
13 catalytic activity and the production of H₂. On the basis of their catalytic activity and
14 H₂ yield the tested catalysts followed this general trend:
15 Rh/Al₂O₃ > Rh(1)/HAP > Rh(2)/HAP > Rh(0.5)/HAP. On the other hand, as checked by
16 XRD and TPO-MS analyses for the post-reaction catalysts, operating with a high
17 H₂O/CH₄ molar ratio (3) did not promote the carbon deposition which might explain
18 their high stability. BET measurements also evidenced that the Rh catalysts did not
19 suffer a significant loss in their surface area. Furthermore, a comparison of the XRD
20 patterns of the freshly reduced and the used catalysts confirmed that there was no
21 alteration of their crystalline structure.

22

23 **3.9. Discussion**

24 From the analysis of the catalytic data, in both POM and SRM reactions, it is clear that,
25 among all tested Rh/HAP samples, the catalyst with the optimum loading of 1% is the

1 most active one. The better behaviour of this sample might be related to the distribution
2 of the Rh species and the improved textural properties compared to the rest of the
3 catalysts (Rh(0.5)/HAP and Rh(2)/HAP). As shown by the different characterisation
4 techniques, these interesting properties could be provided by an initial distribution of
5 the Rh species, in the freshly calcined sample, characterised by a low contribution of the
6 incorporated Rh species in the HAP structure. This is because the reduction of
7 incorporated Rh provoked a phase transformation from HAP to TCP which significantly
8 lowered the activity of the metallic Rh. In this sense, we thought that the interaction of
9 Rh with TCP phase seemed to have a negative impact on the catalyst activity.

10 On the other hand, it is worth highlighting the interest of the Rh(1)/HAP sample as an
11 alternative highly active and coke-resistant catalyst to the conventional Rh/Al₂O₃. The
12 former possessed a relatively lower specific surface area (27 m² g⁻¹ vs. 125 m² g⁻¹ on the
13 Rh/Al₂O₃) and a lower dispersion of Rh (11.6% vs 32% on the Rh/Al₂O₃). Despite this
14 fact the catalytic performance of the Rh(1)/HAP sample in SRM appeared as good as
15 that of the commercial Rh/Al₂O₃. One could attribute this comparable behaviour to
16 suitable properties provided by HAP support such as reducibility, peculiar surface
17 chemistry and some textural properties which might compensate the low dispersion of
18 the Rh active phase induced by its low specific surface area. Indeed, in contrast to
19 alumina, the H₂-TPR results showed that the HAP support exhibited relatively high
20 reducibility with a reversible character. Regarding the acid-base properties, though
21 quantitative information revealed that HAP and alumina supports had comparable basic
22 properties, the difference between them mainly is the number of the acid sites. The
23 alumina (500 μmol_{NH3} g⁻¹) has an overall acidity 8 times larger than the HAP support
24 (62 μmol_{NH3} g⁻¹). We also thought that, operating at relatively high temperatures, the
25 pore size (42-48 nm) exhibited by the series of the Rh/HAP samples might be beneficial

1 for their catalytic performance. In this sense, these large pore sizes (4 times larger than
2 that of Rh/Al₂O₃, Table 1) could ensure a better diffusion of the reactants and the
3 products during the SRM reaction.

4 **4. Conclusions**

6 Highly active and stable Rh/hydroxyapatite samples prepared by impregnation were
7 investigated for the partial oxidation and steam reforming of methane. The catalysts
8 were analysed by BET, XRD, DRS, XPS, H₂-TPR, TEM, H₂ chemisorption, CO₂-TPD
9 and NH₃-TPD techniques. The characterisation results showed that, after calcination, Rh
10 existed in three different forms in the samples: (i) large crystallites of Rh₂O₃ deposited
11 on the surface of catalysts, (ii) RhO_x in small particles exhibiting strong interaction with
12 the support and (iii) a phase of Rh²⁺ species which incorporated the hydroxyapatite
13 framework. After reduction at 1000 K, the structural and textural properties of the
14 catalysts seemed to depend on the distribution of the Rh among these three different
15 sites. The reduction of the incorporated Rh provoked a phase transformation from HAP
16 to TCP which significantly lowered the specific surface area of the catalysts. However,
17 the catalyst with the lowest contribution of these species (Rh(1)/HAP) showed a good
18 resistance against the loss of its specific surface area due to its higher structural
19 stability.

20 Operating in the POM and SRM processes the Rh(x)/HAP catalysts resulted highly
21 active and exhibited excellent stability at 973 K in the studied time on stream (30 h).
22 This behaviour was explained by their high coke-resistance. However, the interaction of
23 Rh with TCP phase seemed to have a negative impact on the catalyst activity. The
24 activity of the catalyst with the optimum loading (1%) was compared with that of a
25 commercial Rh/Al₂O₃ catalyst. The conversion levels and H₂ and CO yields achieved on

1 the former were very close. This comparable behaviour was explained by suitable
2 properties provided by the HAP support such as reducibility, lower surface acidity and
3 larger pore sizes (ensuring a better diffusion of the reactants and the products during the
4 SRM reaction). These properties seemed to compensate the low dispersion of the Rh
5 active phase induced by its low specific surface area.

6

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13

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1 CAPTIONS FOR TABLES AND FIGURES

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- Table 2 H₂-TPR data for the calcined Rh(x)/HAP catalysts.
- Table 3 XPS data for the calcined Rh(x)/HAP catalysts.
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- Table 5 Data of NH₃-TPD and CO₂-TPD studies over the reduced Rh(x)/HAP samples.
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- Figure 1 Pore size distribution for the (-c) calcined and (-r) reduced catalysts
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- Figure 5 DRS spectra for the calcined Rh(x)/HAP catalysts.
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- Figure 7 (a) CO₂-TPD and (b) NH₃-TPD profiles of the reduced Rh(x)/HAP catalysts.
- Figure 8 Methane conversion (a) and H₂ (b), CO (c) and CO₂ (d) yields over reduced Rh(x)/HAP catalysts versus reaction temperature in the POM reaction. Reaction conditions: 19,200 cm³ CH₄ g⁻¹ h⁻¹; W = 0.250 g. Gas mixture: 10%CH₄/5%O₂/N₂.
- Figure 9 Activity and products distribution over reduced Rh(0.5)/HAP and Rh(1)/HAP catalysts versus time on stream in the POM reaction. Reaction conditions: 19,200 cm³ CH₄ g⁻¹ h⁻¹; W = 0.250 g, T = 973 K. Gas mixture: 10%CH₄/5%O₂/N₂.
- Figure 10 Methane conversion (a) and H₂ (b), CO (c) and CO₂ (d) yields over reduced Rh(x)/HAP catalysts versus reaction temperature in the SRM reaction. Reaction conditions: 19,200 cm³ CH₄ g⁻¹ h⁻¹; W = 0.250 g. Gas mixture: 10%CH₄/30%H₂O/N₂. Data corresponding to the commercial Rh/Al₂O₃ catalyst were also included.
- Figure 11 Methane conversion (a) and H₂ (b), CO (c) and CO₂ (d) yields over reduced Rh(x)/HAP catalysts versus time on stream in the SRM reaction. Reaction

conditions: $19,200 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ CH}_4 \text{ g}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$; $W = 0.250 \text{ g}$; $T = 973 \text{ K}$. Gas mixture: $10\% \text{ CH}_4 / 30\% \text{ H}_2\text{O} / \text{N}_2$. Data corresponding to the commercial $\text{Rh}/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ catalyst and thermodynamic equilibrium were also included.

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Catalysts	$S_{\text{BET}}, \text{m}^2 \text{g}^{-1}$	$V_p, \text{cm}^3 \text{g}^{-1}$	dp, nm	(a \pm 0.02), Å	(c \pm 0.002), Å	V, Å ³	d _{HAP} , nm ^(c)
HAP	30 ^(a)	0.29	38	9.3701	6.8188	518.5	49
	33 ^(b)	0.30	33	9.3692	6.8144	518.0	32
Rh(0.5)/HAP	31 ^(a)	0.29	36	9.3845	6.8216	520.3	44
	26 ^(b)	0.27	40	9.3810	6.8181	519.6	47
Rh(1)/HAP	31 ^(a)	0.26	32	9.3965	6.8168	521.2	39
	30 ^(b)	0.30	37	9.3974	6.8073	520.6	43
Rh(2)/HAP	30 ^(a)	0.27	35	9.4314	6.7945	523.4	37
	25 ^(b)	0.24	37	9.4328	6.7948	523.6	39
Rh/Al ₂ O ₃	132 ^(a)	0.42	10				
	125 ^(b)	0.35	9				

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(a) Samples calcined at 1000 K.

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(b) Samples reduced at 1000 K.

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(c) HAP crystallite size calculated according to Scherrer equation.

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Table 1

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Catalysts	Total reducibility, $\mu\text{mol}_{\text{H}_2} \text{g}^{-1}$	Rh reducibility, $\mu\text{mol}_{\text{H}_2} \text{g}^{-1(\text{a})}$	H_2/Rh	Reducibility of the Rh species		
				α , $\mu\text{mol}_{\text{H}_2} \text{g}^{-1(\text{b})}$	β , $\mu\text{mol}_{\text{H}_2} \text{g}^{-1(\text{b})}$	γ , $\mu\text{mol}_{\text{H}_2} \text{g}^{-1(\text{b})}$
HAP	209	0	-	0	0	0
Rh(0.5)/HAP	289	62	1.2	31 (50%) ^(c)	15 (24%)	16 (26%)
Rh(1)/HAP	360	115	1.2	60 (52%)	35 (31%)	20 (17%)
Rh(2)/HAP	507	256	1.3	141 (55%)	59 (23%)	56 (22%)

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(a) As determined by integration of the peaks assigned to Rh species (Fig. 3).

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(b) As determined by integration of the peak assigned to each Rh species (Fig. 3).

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(c) Values in brackets correspond to the contribution of this phase to the total amounts of consumed H_2 .

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Table 2

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XPS

Catalysts	Rh, % (ICP)	Rh, % (XPS)	Ca/P	Rh (3d _{5/2}), eV	Rh (3d _{3/2}), eV	Ca 2p, eV	P 2p, eV	O 1s, eV
HAP	0	0	1.5	-	-	346.8	133.4	530.8
Rh(0.5)/HAP	0.5	0.5	1.6	307.9	312.6	346.2	133.9	530.0
Rh(1)/HAP	1.0	0.9	1.5	307.8	312.4	346.2	134.6	530.1
Rh(2)/HAP	2.0	1.4	1.5	307.7	312.2	346.0	134.3	530.2

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Table 3

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Catalysts	TEM			H ₂ chemisorption		
	$d_{\text{TEM}}, \text{nm}^{(a)}$	$D_{\text{TEM}}, \%^{(a)}$	$S_{\text{Rh}}, \text{m}^2 \text{g}^{-1(a)}$	$d_{\text{chem}}, \text{nm}^{(b)(c)}$	$D_{\text{chem}}, \%^{(b)}$	$S_{\text{Rh}}, \text{m}^2 \text{g}^{-1(b)}$
Rh(0.5)/HAP	12.8	10.6	0.18	7.9	17	0.28
Rh(1)/HAP	11.6	11.6	0.38	14	9.6	0.32
Rh(2)/HAP	16.2	8.3	0.55	21.1	6.4	0.42
Rh/Al ₂ O ₃	-	-	-	3.6	32	1.06

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(a) As determined by TEM techniques.

(b) As determined by H₂ chemisorption experiments at 313 K.

(c) Calculated according to Eq. (3) and Eq. (4).

Table 4

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Catalysts	Surface acidity, $\mu\text{mol}_{\text{NH}_3} \text{m}^{-2}$	Surface basicity, $\mu\text{mol}_{\text{CO}_2} \text{m}^{-2}$	Weak basic sites, % (390-440 K)	Medium basic sites, % (500-600 K)	Strong basic sites, % (> 700 K)
HAP	2.3	2.7	26	55	19
Rh(0.5)/HAP	1.2	3.1	28	63	9
Rh(1)/HAP	1.2	2.2	44	47	9
Rh(2)/HAP	1.5	2.0	53	39	8

Table 5

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Reaction	Catalyst	T ₅₀ , K	H ₂ /CO			CO/CO ₂		
			773 K	873 K	973 K	773 K	873 K	973 K
<u>POM</u>	Rh(0.5)/HAP	886	3.4	2.6	2.1	0.2	1.1	3.8
	Rh(1)/HAP	860	3.4	2.5	2.1	0.5	1.5	4.6
	Rh(2)/HAP	910	2.6	3.1	2.1	0.4	0.4	4.2
	Equilibrium	850	10.8	3.7	2.3	0.5	2.4	14.7
<u>SRM</u>	Rh(0.5)/HAP	910	19.4	10.8	6.9	0.2	0.5	1.0
	Rh(1)/HAP	845	19.9	8.9	5.8	0.2	0.7	1.5
	Rh(2)/HAP	860	19.9	9.9	6.4	0.2	0.5	1.1
	Rh/Al ₂ O ₃	830	21.6	9.4	5.6	0.2	0.6	1.2
	Equilibrium	750	21.1	8.2	5.9	0.2	0.8	1.4

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Table 6

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 6

Figure 7

Figure 8

Figure 9

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Figure 10

Figure 11